

**Developing a Gender-Aware Framework for the
Implementation and Integration of Gender Equality Plans in
Business and Management Schools**

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Title: Developing a Gender-Aware Framework for the Implementation and Integration of Gender Equality Plans in Business and Management Schools**Authors: Yunyan Li*, Valerie Stead, Sophie Alkhaled, Claire Leitch, Eleni Apospori, Nancy Pouloudi, Mariangela Trompeta, Ella Oelbrandt, Jan De Schamphelre, Christophe Vanroelen, Jelena Angelia, Sarah Jack, Paraskevi Dimakou, Fida Afiouni and Yasmeen Makarem****Abstract**

There have been persistent efforts to tackle gender inequalities (GE) in higher education, and yet women remain under-represented in all disciplines and at all levels of academia, especially in senior leadership roles (Shepherd, 2017; Fotaki, 2013). Since 2015, the EU has been actively supporting the development and implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in academic organisations as a tool for structural change (Clavero & Galligan, 2021). A GEP is defined as a set of actions aimed at identifying gender inequalities and bias, designing and implementing measures to correct these, and setting targets and monitoring progress via indicators (EIGE, 2016). GEPs implemented in the context of EU funded projects must meet the three objectives of the European Research Area in relation to gender equality: (1) to remove legal and other barriers to the recruitment, retention, and career progression of female researchers; (2) to address gender imbalances in decision making processes, and (3) to strengthen the gender dimension in research (Council of the European Union, 2015; Clavero and Galligan, 2021). While GE work has focused mainly on STEMM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, and Medicine) subjects, little research has explored the effectiveness or reach of these gender equality initiatives in Business and management (B&M) schools (Roseberry et al., 2016).

This paper adopts an innovative methodology to developing, implementing and monitoring GEPs in five business and management schools in Greece, UK, Sweden, Belgium, and Lebanon as part of the TARGETED-MPI project funded by Horizon 2020 program (2020- 2024). To delve deeper into the tensions between the gendered relationship between ‘culture and structure’ in the male-dominated business and management schools (Ślíwa et al., 2022), this paper develops a unique diagnostic tool for investigating the persistence of gender inequality despite the rise in various Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) initiatives across the schools. It does so by adopting Johnson and Scholes (1988) Cultural Web methodology, through a gender-aware lens (Shymko et al., 2023). The gender-aware analysis of the interviews and focus groups with academics and senior management reveals that insufficient attention has been paid to the role of gendered power relations in maintaining gender inequality at all institutional levels, and to the role of organisational culture in the perpetuation of gender inequalities within and across departments in B&M schools. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of approaching gender inequality as a point of tension between the organisational culture and the power structures, rather than merely focusing on EDI policy development within the university. The study suggests that the incorporation of a gender-aware lens in understanding (female and male) academics’ experiences in each institutional context can lead to the creation of bespoke GEPs, which provide a solid EDI framework, grounded and

situated within each institutional context, to tackle the embedded gendered power relations and lead to sustainable equitable outcomes.